

The humanitarian crisis in Gaza: a tragic nexus of health, mortality, and economic struggles

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ABSTRACT: Purpose of the study: This study investigates into the complex consequences of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict on Gaza, particularly scrutinizing its profound effects on the region's economy, poverty levels, mortality rates, and overall health catalogues. The prolonged conflict and the imposition of an Israeli blockade have caused a dire reduction in medical services, resulting in elevated mortality rates and a distressing flow in poverty levels. Notably, esteemed organizations such as the World Bank, UNDP, and Oxfam have precisely examined various facets of poverty in Gaza, underscoring the urgent need for sustainable development solutions. The periodic propagation of living condition and poverty rate data by the Palestinian Central Bureau of Statistics (PCBS) has proven instrumental in shaping public policy and intervention strategies. The toxic impact of poverty echoes through heightened food insecurity, inadequate housing, and restricted access to quality healthcare and education, significantly affecting the mental well-being of individuals and families.

Methodology and Design of the Study: Utilizing a comprehensive narrative approach, this study amalgamates research findings, reports, and statistical data to delineate the multifaceted impact of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict on Gaza. Drawing from the rigorous analyses undertaken by esteemed organizations, the study underscores the imperative of addressing the root causes of the conflict, eliminating the blockade, and fostering sustainable economic development. This study emphasizes the pressing need for collaborative efforts with international organizations, NGOs, and local initiatives to safeguard the rights and well-being of Gaza's inhabitants. Through a meticulous review of existing literature and research, the study aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the diverse impacts of the conflict, emphasizing the profound influence of poverty on the health, mortality, and overall well-being of the local population.

Findings of the Study: The study reveals a distressing pattern of reduced medical services, heightened mortality rates, and rising poverty levels as direct consequences of the conflict and blockade. The study underscores the urgent requirement for sustainable development strategies, unconstrained availability of healthcare services, and economic prospects to alleviate the substantial difficulties faced by the population in Gaza. This study also highlights the correlation between poverty and adverse outcomes, such as high levels of food insecurity, inadequate housing, and restricted access to quality healthcare and education, with profound implications for the mental well-being of individuals and families.

Future Recommendations of the Study: Based on the findings, the study advocates for a series of actionable recommendations to address the challenges in Gaza. These involve enabling the restriction, supporting regional reconstruction and growth, ensuring unrestricted access to healthcare services, and fostering economic development. Additionally, the study emphasizes the necessity of enhancing the healthcare system's capacity to manage emergencies and public health issues, advocating for training initiatives for healthcare professionals, and streamlining the import process of medical supplies and equipment. Ultimately, the study underscores the imperative of promoting economic prospects in Gaza to enhance living conditions and combat poverty, emphasizing the pivotal role of sustainable development strategies in addressing the overarching difficulties faced by the local population.

Keywords: Health, Mortality, Economic Struggles, Israel- Palestine war, Gaza Crises

Introduction
Mortality Rates in Gaza
Concerns and International Attention
High Unemployment Rates
Conclusion
Policy Recommendations
References

At a hospital in Khan Yunis, located in the southern Gaza Strip, on October 24. | Photo Credit: MAHMUD HAMS/AFP

1. Introduction

Unveiling the Israeli-Palestinian Conflict: Gaza's Struggle and Impact:

The prolonged geopolitical confrontation between Israel and Palestine has significantly impacted the lives of Palestinians, especially those living in Gaza. The war is caused by conflicting national interests and territorial conflicts, resulting in bloodshed, political standstills, and humanitarian catastrophes (Ziv, 2024). Historically, war has focused on the Gaza Strip, a densely populated coastal region in the eastern Mediterranean (Calandri & Golemo, 2023). Multiple battles and military operations have taken place since Israel's occupation of the area in 1967, leading to substantial human suffering and a worsening humanitarian situation. The Israeli-Palestinian war has had a substantial impact on Gaza's economy, mortality rates, and health. The interlinked aspects worsen the issues affecting the population by reinforcing each other (World Bank, 2023). The Israeli-Palestinian conflict stems from conflicting national aspirations and territorial claims between Jews and Arabs in Palestine (Gelvin, 2014; Perry, 2023). Numerous Palestinians were displaced and lost their homes and means of living due to the creation of the State of Israel in 1948 and subsequent Arab-Israeli conflicts, leading to ongoing animosities that persist to this day. Maharashwamy (2023). The Gaza Strip, inhabited by over two million Palestinians, has a long history of conflict. Since Israel's withdrawal in 2005, both Israel and Egypt have imposed an embargo on the region, significantly limiting the movement of persons and commodities. The political division between Fatah and Hamas, Palestinian factions, along with the continuous closure of Gaza, have led to elevated unemployment rates, economic standstill, and reliance on external assistance. Infrastructure in Gaza has suffered significant damage, particularly during the conflicts between Israel and Hamas (Kurz & Berti, 2018). The military operations under consideration are the Israel-Gaza confrontation in May 2021, Operation Pillar of Defence in 2012, and Operation Cast Lead in 2008–2009 (Morag, 2023). Casualties, home destruction, and damage to infrastructure, such as schools, hospitals, and water systems, have occurred due to military actions in Gaza. The UN has consistently expressed worries about the severe humanitarian conditions in the region (Fahmy, 2023). Many studies have shown the challenges faced by individuals in Gaza in obtaining safe drinking water, sufficient medical care, and educational possibilities. The Gaza Strip, with one of the greatest population densities globally, worsens preexisting problems. International organizations have utilized diplomatic attempts, peace plans, and negotiations over time to resolve the conflict between Israelis and Palestinians (Dinar, 2003; Jafari, 2020). A definitive resolution to the Israeli-Palestinian issue remains elusive despite attempts. Unresolved concerns include the status of Jerusalem, the Palestinian refugees' right of return, and the establishment of an independent Palestinian state. The intricacy and toll on human lives of this conflict are most effectively demonstrated by the circumstances in Gaza. The international community aims to resolve this problem equitably and permanently. The United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA, 2023) reports that Gaza's healthcare system is significantly affected by the blockade. Gaza's healthcare capacity has been greatly diminished due to constraints on importing medical supplies and equipment (OCHA, 2023).

Figure 1

ISRAEL/PALESTINE

Palestinians expelled

In 1948, Zionist military forces expelled at least **750,000** Palestinians and captured **78 percent of historic Palestine**. The remaining 22 percent was divided into the West Bank and Gaza Strip.

In Figure 1 shows the development of what is now known as Palestine, which includes the Gaza Strip and the West Bank, which are governed by Israel and the Palestinians. It also shows changes in who has control over certain areas. It illustrates five major historical occurrences that show how big the Israeli-Palestinian conflict is and how much land Israel currently occupies. The 1917 image shows that Jewish authority over Palestine accounted for barely 6% of the entire geographical area (the green zone) prior to the British Mandate. After the state of Israel was established in 1948, Palestine experienced profound changes. About 750,000 Palestinians were forcibly removed from their homes by Zionist forces, and 78% of historic Palestine was absorbed by Israel. The green areas on the map represent Israeli sovereignty, while the tan areas stand for Palestinian rule. Israel seized control of the West Bank and Gaza after the Six-Day War broke out in June 1967. An extra 300,000 Palestinians were forced from their homes by the occupation. The areas that Israel has taken over during the conflict are represented by the growing green areas on the map.

The West Bank was divided into three separate regions by the Oslo Accords of 1995. Area C was taken over by Israel, Area B saw the establishment of a combined Israeli-Palestinian authority, and Area A was given to Palestine. These divisions were represented on the map by a variety of brown color schemes and patterned patterns. In 2020, US President Donald Trump proposed a plan that would enable Israel to annex significant portions of the occupied West Bank. Under this plan, the Palestinians would have control over only 15% of historic Palestine, while the rest would be under Israeli control. In the map, the green areas represent the regions under Israeli control, and the small tan patches depict the areas that would be under Palestinian control according to this plan.

Navigating Crisis: Gaza's Health, Mortality, blockade and Economic Challenges:

Medical supplies like medicines, surgical tools, and diagnostic devices are scarce due to the Gaza embargo. These shortages have made it difficult for hospitals to diagnose, treat, and care for patients. (OCHA, 2023). The World Health Organization says the Gaza embargo has hampered health infrastructure development and maintenance. Due to limited availability to building materials and equipment, healthcare facilities have struggled to build and upgrade to satisfy population healthcare needs (WHO, 2019). Healthcare experts are also hard to hire and keep due to the Gaza barrier. Low medical supplies and equipment and difficult working circumstances have deterred healthcare personnel from practicing in the area, resulting in a shortage of trained practitioners (OCHA, 2022). The Gazans have suffered greatly from these healthcare constraints. Delays in medical care lead to inadequate treatment, diagnosis, and higher morbidity and mortality rates. Children, pregnant women, and chronically ill people, who need healthcare 24/7, have been severely harmed by the blockage (WHO, 2019). Gaza's healthcare system is significantly hampered by the embargo. Gaza's healthcare services are hindered by limited medical supplies and equipment, infrastructure development, and personnel retention. These restrictions have greatly harmed population health, especially the most vulnerable. The blockade has hampered crucial medical services. Some affected healthcare services are listed here. Gaza lacks crucial pharmaceuticals due to limited medical supply entrance. Chronic illness patients like diabetes, hypertension, and cancer sometimes have trouble getting their meds. This was noted by WHO in 2019. Diagnostic tools including imaging machines and lab supplies are scarce due to the blockage. In 2023, OCHA reported delays and limits in diagnostic tests, making it difficult to effectively diagnose and treat medical issues." Healthcare facilities' surgery performance is greatly impacted by surgical instrument and equipment shortages. Lack of funding limits urgent procedures like trauma surgery and cancer therapies. The WHO reported this in 2019. The Gaza siege has hurt maternity and child healthcare. Due to a lack of medical supplies and equipment and difficulty receiving professional care, pregnancy and delivery risks have increased. Shorrab noted in 2023 that the blockage has hampered vaccines, infant care, and pediatric healthcare. Mental health services and physical resources have been hampered by the Gaza barrier. Gazans are more likely to have mental health illnesses due to political and economic issues and restricted mental healthcare resources. Unfortunately, mental health experts and therapy medications are few (WHO, 2019).

Gaza's siege and import restrictions make medical supplies and equipment scarce. Delays or obstacles in obtaining critical items cause shortages and irregular availability. Importing medical goods is expensive, complicating procurement and increasing resource scarcity (Smith, 2015). Medical equipment maintenance and repair in Gaza is difficult due to a lack of spare parts and professional skills. Equipment breakdowns can take a long time to fix, worsening the equipment scarcity (Radwan, 2012). Gaza's diagnostic and medical services are hampered by the situation. The Gaza healthcare system relies on foreign and humanitarian donations of medical supplies and equipment. Although these donations bridge gaps, more is needed to meet the increasing need. Al-Khaldi et al. (2020). Healthcare systems often struggle to deliver specialized care when donated materials don't always meet their demands. The requirement for more medical supplies and equipment also hinders healthcare innovation and technology adoption. Healthcare practitioners need the latest technology to give cutting-edge treatments and interventions, improving patient care (Smith, 2015). Limited medical supplies including gloves, masks, and sterile equipment raise the risk of healthcare-associated infections in hospitals. Insufficient infection prevention and control due to resource constraints can compromise patient safety and results (Elmadhoun, 2011). Gazan healthcare staff struggle to train and advance due to a scarcity of medical supplies. Patients may have to leave Gaza or use foreign healthcare providers for specialized therapies or modern medical technologies. It causes unequal

healthcare access and poor results (Jabari et al., 2023). A comprehensive approach is needed to address Gaza's medical supply and equipment shortage. Build infrastructure, strengthen supply chains, promote production, and remove limitations that limit access to key resources. Addressing these issues can enhance Gaza's healthcare services, improving population health.

Health Conditions in Gaza

Destruction of Medical Infrastructure

Gaza's population lacks healthcare due to the loss of its medical facilities. The region's ongoing hostilities and military actions have damaged hospitals, clinics, and pharmacies. Thus, delivering proper medical treatment in the region is difficult (Abu Hamad et al., 2023). Warring groups sometimes target hospital infrastructure. This destroys or damages medical facilities, preventing them from providing crucial healthcare to the impacted population. Long-term ramifications of such destruction follow the fight. After the conflict, damaged or destroyed healthcare facilities struggle to recover and rebuild, causing long-term service disruptions. Conflict-damaged healthcare infrastructure can take years to rebuild (Alrayyes, 2023). The loss of hospitals and clinics substantially reduces medical care. It restricts emergency care, surgeries, and specialist treatments and disturbs chronic illness patients' regular medical appointments and pharmaceutical availability. Medical equipment such diagnostic machines, lab facilities, and surgical instruments is also destroyed (Mahomed, 2023). The destruction of pharmacies and pharmaceutical storage facilities in Gaza makes proper diagnosis, timely treatments, and surgical interventions impossible. This causes a lack of chronic and acute disease drugs and supplies. The damage of Gaza's medical infrastructure also affects public health. Limitations on life-saving therapies, preventive care, and emergency services worsen healthcare issues and hinder access to proper care. Gaza's medical infrastructure must be rebuilt to provide crucial services. However, political and economic issues and the siege are slowing reconstruction and healthcare recovery in Gaza (Goodarzi & Hassan, 2023). Gaza's medical infrastructure is damaged, causing widespread healthcare issues. Emergency, specialist, and surgical services have been severely limited in the region due to the loss of hospitals, clinics, and medical facilities. According to Ahmed's 2023 assessment found that healthcare facility devastation had impacted chronic disease and continuous medical care. The healthcare system is overwhelmed by the influx of patients at hospitals that survived the wars. Their care quality has suffered as a result. Critical medical equipment and supplies have been lost or damaged due to medical infrastructure destruction. Diagnostic devices, surgical instruments, and laboratory facilities are scarce, making accurate diagnoses, timely treatments, and necessary surgical interventions difficult (Tsikala et al., 2020). The demolition of pharmacies and pharmaceutical storage facilities might cause drug shortages. This can put patients, especially those with chronic conditions, at risk of not being able to get their treatment drugs. Besides physical health, medical infrastructure loss can affect mental health. Gazans are experiencing more mental health illnesses due to ongoing wars and limited mental healthcare resources. The devastation of medical infrastructure in the region has generated major healthcare issues that are affecting public health. To address Gaza's problems, healthcare facilities must be rebuilt and medical supplies provided. Targeting hospital infrastructure has caused emergency response issues and hindered crucial medical services. Thus, restoring Gazan healthcare is crucial. Compromises in maternal care, immunization, and chronic illness management harm community health (Saad & Dergaa, 2023). Overcrowding, longer wait times, and overworked medical staff have increased as healthcare facilities strain. This has lowered medical treatment quality. The displacement of healthcare workers owing to safety concerns or facility issues has exacerbated the scarcity of educated medical staff (Tsikala et al., 2020). Infrastructure damage can disrupt medication supply systems, making drugs hard to get. This causes uncontrolled chronic diseases and preventable health complications. Healthcare system

breakdowns can make it hard to control communicable diseases, especially in displaced people without medical care. Damage to healthcare facilities can generate worry, anxiety, and trauma, which can harm mental health. Conflicts make it hard for people to get cancer treatments and operations, delaying or preventing them. This can cause long-term morbidity, chronic disease, and humanitarian crises. To address the multiple issues created by conflict-related medical infrastructure destruction and protect affected communities, healthcare systems must be rebuilt and strengthened (Diab et al., 2023).

2. Mortality Rates in Gaza

Loss of Civilian Lives

Collateral Damage: Civilian Vulnerability in Conflict-Ridden Gaza

The Palestinian Ministry of Health (MoH) death toll has been questioned throughout the Gaza crisis (Tétrault-Farber, 2023). To address this, we studied 7,028 deaths between October 7 and 3:00 PM on October 26, 2023. According to Haddad (2023), the Palestinian MoH issued the list of deceased people with national identity numbers, names, and ages, but only those taken to hospitals or morgues. Nobody mentioned the reason, date, or location of death. The list's data quality was reasonable when we first examined it. One duplicate identity number, one improbable age, and 281 unidentified fatalities were found. Four percent of the records were eliminated from further analysis. As is customary with Palestinian naming, we kept six records with the same names but different ages. A high association between identification numbers and age was established, with three diagonal patterns indicating consecutive identification numbers for adults aged 0-29 (birth years 1994-2023), 30-40 (1983-93), and 41-50 (1973-82). We also found three horizontal patterns that may indicate an earlier cross-sectional registration mechanism for those over 50 and two subsequent catch-up registrations. Data fabrication is unlikely to explain the observed patterns. Most deaths (4594 out of 6745) were children under 18, women 18–59, or men and women over 60. These organizations rarely contain combatants. They contributed 68.1% to deaths. We used UN Population Fund forecasts to compute 20-day death rates for each age group and gender. This forecast was based on 2017 census data, which assumed a 2% undercount and predicted a 33% fertility decrease and 50% infant mortality reduction between 2017 and 2023. August 24, 2023, The Humanitarian Data Exchange provided the data. Mortality rose with age, peaking in men aged 30–34, probably due to combatant or civilian exposures. Based on Palestinian MoH data, mortality rates for men and women aged 20–59 were similar to the crude mortality rate in the same age bracket among UNRWA employees (teachers, healthcare workers, and other staff), UN, 2023 as reported independently by UNRWA staff in Gaza to their headquarters in Jordan. The Palestinian Ministry of Health and Palestinian Central Bureau of Statistics announced healthcare worker crude death rates in 2013 and 2023. These comparisons support the Palestinian MoH dataset. Sky News' satellite imagery-based estimations of Gaza's building damage from NASA Open Street Maps match the Gaza Ministry of Public Works' 7% estimate. Due to violence, military operations, and the vulnerability of densely populated areas to armed confrontations, Gaza's civilian mortality statistics are alarming (Mosleh et al., 2018). The Gaza Strip has seen many military operations and civilian deaths (Mosleh et al., 2018). Airstrikes, shelling, and ground assaults can damage infrastructure and kill people in these conflicts (Shorrab et al., 2023). Violence's direct and indirect effects are especially harmful to civilians like women, children, and the elderly (Jofr et al., 2024). Violence that targets people causes direct casualties (KINIK et al., 2024). Airstrikes, explosions, shootings, and other armed attacks cause deaths (BAYRAK et al., 2024). Explosive weapons in densely populated locations make it difficult to discern combatants from non-combatants, increasing civilian casualties (Montasari, 2024). The wider impact of military wars causes indirect casualties. Destroying hospitals, water and sanitation systems, and energy networks causes mortality (Shorrab et al., 2023). Lack of healthcare, potable water, and sanitation

can raise mortality rates (Al-Khaldi et al., 2021). Armed conflicts in densely populated areas place vulnerable populations, such as children, women, the elderly, and individuals with disabilities, at a higher risk of mortality (Carpiniello, 2023). These groups may struggle to seek shelter, access healthcare, and receive necessary assistance during conflicts (Shorrab et al., 2023). Children, in particular, bear a significant burden, as they are more susceptible to trauma, injuries, and the long-term consequences of violence (Jones, 2023).

Challenges in healthcare delivery:

Gaza has significant fatality rates due to medical infrastructure destruction and insufficient supplies and equipment (Ahmed, 2023). The weakened healthcare system delays emergency care, increasing conflict injury mortality (Abu Qamar, 2023). Trauma care and major procedures can reduce survival rates without access (Shorrab, 2023). In addition to killing people, Kinik et al. (2024) say the Gaza conflict has psychological effects. Traumatic incidents, loss of loved ones, and continual worry and insecurity can cause PTSD, anxiety, and depression. Psychology might indirectly affect death rates by increasing suicide, self-harm, and chronic health issues (Jabr et al., 2023). Death rates in Gaza are higher due to the vulnerability of densely populated areas to armed conflicts (Saad & Dergaa, 2023). Urban explosive weapons use increases civilian casualties and collateral damage, especially in densely populated regions (Buheji & Mushimiyimana, 2023). Gazan inhabitants must be protected during violent crises, given access to key services, infrastructure rebuilt, and their mental health and well-being supported (Shorrab, 2023). International humanitarian organisations, governments, and stakeholders must work together to promote peace and give resources to reduce Gazan mortality rates from violent conflicts (Taha & Anabtawi, 2024).

3. Concerns and International Attention

Global awareness of the high number of casualties and fatalities

Gaza's high casualties and deaths have garnered international attention (Al-Muhannadi & Buheji, 2024). War and military actions have killed civilians, prompting calls for action to alleviate the humanitarian crisis in the region (Yadlin & Evental, 2024). Violence against Gazan civilians has been a concern for the UN and human rights organisations (Samudzi, 2024). These organisations' research emphasises accountability and respect for international humanitarian law owing to civilian casualties (Alquhaly & Basir, 2023). Operation Protective Edge, the 2014 Israel-Hamas confrontation, was notable. The majority of the 2,251 Palestinians killed in the conflict were civilians, including 551 children, according to a 2015 UN study. The 2023 assessment accused both sides of employing disproportionate force and violating international humanitarian law (Nagy, 2023). Amnesty International has also denounced Gaza's high civilian deaths and human rights abuses (Sayigh, 2024). They have documented the effects of Israeli airstrikes, shelling, and explosive weapons in highly populated places (Shorrab, 2023). They want international probes into war crimes and accountability for all parties (Yadlin & Evental, 2024). Human Rights Watch also worries about disproportionate force and international law violations in Gaza (Reddhirman, 2024). Israeli soldiers have targeted homes and schools, killing civilians (Stockton, 2024). Independent inquiries into suspected violations are needed to ensure distinction and proportionality in armed situations (Szapak & Kolodziejska, 2023). The international community is concerned about Gaza. The UN Security Council and General Assembly have called for civilian protection, international humanitarian law, and a peaceful settlement to the war (Assembly et al., 2015). International Criminal Court (ICC) investigations into regional war crimes and crimes against humanity have begun. This analysis shows international legal scrutiny (Reddhirman, 2024). Global attention has been drawn to Gaza's high casualties and deaths, raising concerns about excessive force and human rights breaches (Yamin, 2024). UN, Amnesty International, and Human Rights

Watch reports have recorded civilian suffering and asked for accountability (Mhajne, 2024). The ICC and international organisations have stressed the necessity of preserving international humanitarian law and protecting civilians (Antouly & Mignot-Mahdavi, 2024). The international community must resolve the Gaza conflict peacefully and protect civilians (Shorrab, 2023). Gaza's high casualties and deaths, together with claims of disproportionate force and human rights breaches, have garnered international attention (Obermaier, 2024).

International diplomatic efforts:

The Israeli-Palestinian conflict, particularly Gaza, has long concerned the world community (Loewenstein & Moor, 2024). Negotiations, peace initiatives, and international conferences try to resolve the conflict's core causes (Ezugwu, 2023). The continuous violence and civilian deaths in Gaza have made diplomatic attempts difficult (Buheji & Mushimiyimana, 2023). Sambaraju and McVittie's 2024 research found that the UN is examining and reporting on Gaza. Kaufman's 2018 report states that the UN Human Rights Council (UNHRC) has established various independent commissions to probe international law violations during regional crises. Reports of war crimes and human rights abuses have garnered international attention (Eichert, 2024). Gazan population get humanitarian aid from the international community. Countries, international organizations, and NGOs have donated finances, medical supplies, and other essentials to satisfy immediate needs and strengthen the healthcare system (Yadlin & Evental, 2024). These efforts are limited by continued hurdles and limits, therefore sustained international support is needed to alleviate the humanitarian catastrophe (Ben et al., 2022). Gaza inhabitants' rights and protection have been championed by civil society, human rights, and grassroots initiatives. These groups have held rallies, campaigns, and initiatives to raise awareness of the humanitarian issue and urge governments and international organizations, social media has helped victims' voices be heard (Barnes, 2006).

Allegations of violations of international law:

Amnesty International, Human Rights Watch, and B'Tselem have said they've seen excessive force, international humanitarian law violations, and war crimes (Stockton et al., 2024). These organisations have recorded indiscriminate civilian attacks, infrastructure targeting, and disproportionate force (Dil et al., 2024). They want independent investigations and accountability for violators. The ICC is examining Israeli-Palestinian war crimes and crimes against humanity, especially in Gaza (Mhajne, 2024). This judicial scrutiny emphasises accountability and the penalty for major international law infractions (Hassan et al., 2023). The ICC's jurisdiction and ability to resolve the Israeli-Palestinian conflict are still debated. High losses and deaths in Gaza have rekindled international calls for a just and comprehensive Israeli-Palestinian conflict resolution (Schuetze, 2024). It involves resolving the root causes of the conflict, maintaining international law, defending human rights, and protecting people (Dil, 2024). Internationally, the two-state option and substantive negotiations are pushed to achieve sustainable peace (Ziv, 2024; Habib, 2016). High casualties and deaths in Gaza, together with charges of disproportionate force and human rights breaches, have drawn international attention. This prompted diplomatic attempts, probes, and accountability demands (Halewood, 2024). The international community, civil society, and legal procedures must address the Israeli-Palestinian problem. These groups are crucial for awareness, humanitarian aid, and peaceful resolution. Two recent studies by Saaida (2024) and Palmiano et al. (2024) emphasize these efforts.

4. High Unemployment Rates

Economic Strain: Unemployment's Toll on Gaza's Families:

Unemployment in Gaza has exacerbated the economic crisis (Procter et al., 2024). The populace is trapped in poverty, dependency, and social unrest due to a shortage of jobs (Nassar et al., 2023). According to reliable sources, Gaza's unemployment rate remains high (Nhangave, 2024). In the second quarter of 2021, the Palestinian Central Bureau of Statistics recorded 49.1% unemployment for men and women (Al-Khaldi et al., 2021). Youth unemployment is particularly high, at over 65% (De Lannoy et al., 2018). Several factors cause job shortage. Israeli and Egyptian blockades restrict products and supplies, hampering economic growth and entrepreneurship (Sadeh et al., 2024). Trade restrictions prevent enterprises from starting and growing, reducing employment creation (Owda et al., 2019). Infrastructure damage from prior conflicts has also slowed the recovery and development of manufacturing and agriculture, which could have given jobs (Galanakis et al., 2023). High unemployment hurts Gazans and households (Procter, 2024). Without money, people struggle to meet their fundamental requirements like food, housing, healthcare, and education. Families trying to support children become more vulnerable and poorer. Community social fabric is also weakened by unemployment. M. Nijim (2023). Mahamid (2024) states that a lack of meaningful job and economic stability makes people feel forlorn and frustrated. Discontent over lack of chances and unfairness can lead to societal unrest (Martin, J. 2014). Unemployment can cause worthlessness, despair, and poor well-being (Hopkins, K. 2022). Lack of purpose and financial security might harm mental health and quality of life (Walker, 2023). Gaza's significant unemployment necessitates local and international action (Eshtawi et al., 2024). Local organisations and NGOs help small enterprises, encourage entrepreneurship, and offer vocational training to boost employability (Palmer, 2007). International aid programs produce jobs and boost economic growth to sustainably reduce poverty (Awwad et al., 2024). Long-term solutions to the multiple issues need addressing the core causes of the conflict and enacting economic policies (Wambrauw et al., 2024). The international community wants a comprehensive and just settlement to the Israeli-Palestinian conflict that addresses Gazans' economic needs and ambitions (Loewenstein et al., 2024). Follow Al Jazeera, Reuters, BBC, and The Guardian to learn about Gaza's unemployment (Majeed, S. 2008). These sources extensively address the Israeli-Palestinian conflict and its effects on Gaza's economy and jobs (Sadeh et al., 2024). World Bank and UN publications might also shed light on the region's economy and unemployment (Awwad et al., 2024). Lack of official jobs drives many Gazans to the informal economy (Al-Muhannadi et al.; M., 2024). Street vending, small-scale trading, and casual labor are examples. These employments pay, but they are unpredictable, lack social protections, and offer few long-term economic opportunities (Hammami, 1997). Due to limited professional prospects and rising unemployment, Gaza has lost talented workers (McGahern et al., 2024). Displacement of educated and trained workers hinders local economic development (Buheji, M. 2023). Musa (2024) says Gazan women have more trouble finding work. Women's workforce involvement is typically constrained by culture and career possibilities (Elshami et al., 2024). The greater unemployment rate for women in Gaza inhibits their economic empowerment (Althalathini et al., 2020). Gaza's gender disparity and high unemployment rate hamper women's economic empowerment (Althalathini et al., 2020). This support typically falls short of satisfying the population's long-term needs, creating a cycle of reliance (Cardenas et al., 2024). Gaza's youth unemployment is severe due to job shortages (Abudayya, 2023). Youth can become frustrated, disillusioned, and despondent without jobs (Eila, M. 2009). Due to economic hardship and high unemployment, some people have emigrated in quest of opportunities, which might lead to social unrest and radicalization (Laing et al.; S., 2024). The barrier and limited legal migration choices constrain Gazan emigration (Musa, T. 2024). Unemployment can lead to irregular migration,

making people vulnerable (McAuliffe et al., 2017). Job creation, vocational training, and support for small enterprises and entrepreneurship are being used to address Gaza's unemployment crisis (Rufus et al., 2024). International organisations, NGOs, and local initiatives are providing skills training, microfinance, and business development support to boost employment and economic resilience (Baxter et al., 2014). Rettig et al. (2024) emphasize that Gaza's situation is complex and evolving. Follow trustworthy news sources, international organizations, and local NGOs for the latest updates and accurate information. They report on Gaza's economy, unemployment, and solutions (Natil, 2021).

Limited access to resources and markets

The Israeli embargo and protracted Israeli-Palestinian war limit Gazans' access to resources and markets, causing poverty (Romano et al., 2019). Research studies and reports by recognized organisations have shown that poverty has a major impact on Gazan wellbeing and living conditions (Shorrab et al., 2023). World Bank: In-depth World Bank studies on Gazan poverty have shown the terrible economic scenario (Masri et al., 2024). In 2017, Gaza's poverty rate was 53%, greater among youth and female-headed families (Cunningham et al., 2023). Poverty causes food insecurity, poor healthcare and education, and limited economic mobility, according to the World Bank (Chaaban et al., 2010). UNDP research has examined Gazan poverty and living conditions. In their publications, they emphasize that poverty includes income poverty and deprivation in education, health, and housing (Bruch et al., 2024). The UNDP stresses the importance of sustainable development policies that fight poverty and promote social inclusion (Buheji, M., & Khunji, A. 2023). Oxfam has reported on Gaza poverty and the Israeli blockade (Alarabeed, W. 2024). They note that significant limitations on commodities and people travel have damaged the economy and increased aid dependence (Shorrab et al., 2023). Oxfam stresses the importance of ending the blockade and promoting economic opportunities to reduce poverty (Hammad, J., & Tribe, R. 2020). Gazan poverty and living conditions are periodically reported by the PCBS (Migdad, A. M. 2023). Their reports detail income, consumption, and access to key services. These figures provide insights into demographic concerns and inform policymaking (Sadeh, H. S. 2024). Many Gazans lack access to healthful food due to poverty (Shorrab et al., 2023). Over 70% of Gazans are food insecure and depend on outside aid, according to the FAO (Stöber et al., 2024). Gaza lacks cheap and safe homes due to poverty (Knudsen, A. J. 2024). Conflict-related infrastructure loss puts many families in unstable and overcrowded conditions (Chávez et al., 2024). Gazan poverty limits decent education. Poor families struggle to pay for education, books, and transportation (Badawy et al., 2015). This can increase dropout rates and limit children's educational possibilities, prolonging poverty. D.B. Dhiman (2023). Healthcare access is limited by resources and finances. Poverty prevents people from getting medical care and needed medications (Miranda, J., & Green, B. L. 1999). Gaza's healthcare system is further hampered by the blockade's medical supply shortfall (Kooli, C., & Kooli, Y. 2024). Poverty affects mental health in individuals and households. Financial insecurity can exacerbate anxiety, depression, and other mental health concerns (Buheji et al., 2023). Gazan poverty must be addressed by addressing the core causes of the conflict, easing the barrier, and fostering sustainable economic development (Shorrab et al., 2023). International organisations, NGOs, and local efforts help Gazans, promote livelihoods, and advocate for their rights and well-being (Pincock et al., 2024). For Gaza poverty research papers and studies, visit the World Bank, UNDP, Oxfam International, and Palestinian Central Bureau of Statistics websites (Ibrahim, M. 2020). These organisations give vital statistics on how poverty affects Gazan living situations (Shorrab et al., 2023).

5. Conclusion

The Israeli government's use of destructive and aggressive tactics, such as military operations and the ongoing blockade, has had a significant impact on the health, mortality, and economy of Gaza. Reputable international organizations and sources have thoroughly documented this impact.

1. **Health Conditions:** The aggressive approach of Israel has had a severe impact on the health conditions in Gaza. Hospitals and healthcare facilities have been destroyed, which has led to limited access to essential medical services. In addition, there is a shortage of medical supplies and equipment, further hindering the ability to provide adequate healthcare. As a result, morbidity rates have increased, treatment options are limited, and managing public health crises has become increasingly challenging.
2. **Mortality Rates:** The Israeli aggression has led to a significant loss of life in Gaza. Reports indicate that during military operations, civilians, including women and children, have been disproportionately affected. The destruction of residential buildings, schools, and other civilian infrastructure has contributed to a high number of casualties. The loss of lives has a profound impact on families and the community, exacerbating the trauma and psychological distress experienced by the population.
3. **Economic Situation:** The Israeli blockade is a critical strategy that severely limits the movement of goods, services, and people in and out of Gaza. This approach has led to a stagnation of economic growth and development, resulting in high unemployment rates, limited job opportunities, and increased poverty. As a result of the blockade, it has become difficult to establish and expand businesses, impeded trade, and created a dependence on humanitarian aid. The economic situation in Gaza remains fragile, which has long-term consequences on the population's overall well-being.

It is crucial to understand that the situation in Gaza is dynamic and constantly evolving. The conditions on the ground and the geopolitical landscape can significantly impact the population. To stay informed about the latest developments, obtaining up-to-date information from reliable and reputable sources is essential. Some reputable sources for obtaining reliable information on the situation in Gaza include the United Nations, the World Health Organization (WHO), and the United Nations Relief and Works Agency for Palestine Refugees in the Near East (UNRWA).

6. Policy Recommendations

Ending the Blockade:

Ending the Gaza embargo would have major economic and humanitarian benefits. The unrestricted flow of goods would boost trade and economic prosperity. Gaza's economy relies on humanitarian help, and limited market access makes it hard to build sustainable companies. With the siege lifted, Gaza could import and export commodities, boosting its economy and creating jobs. Ending the blockade will boost economic growth and access to crucial commodities and services. Import restrictions have caused food, medication, and fuel shortages in Gaza. The siege might be lifted to allow imports of these important products, increasing Gazans' quality of life and meeting their fundamental requirements. The barrier has also slowed the construction of hospitals, schools, and homes in Gaza. Allowing construction materials imports would help Gaza restore and develop its infrastructure, increasing healthcare, education, and housing. Gazans' well-being and living situations would improve. Helping individuals move is crucial to lifting the blockade. Travel restrictions in and out of Gaza hamper education, employment, and specialized medical care. Gazans might seek educational and professional possibilities outside the territory with freedom of movement, improving their personal and Gazan development. While removing the embargo is necessary, all sides should also take security

measures. Preventing arms smuggling while permitting free trade is possible with these techniques. Balancing security needs with Gazan rights can lead to a more durable and just solution. Finally, lifting the Gaza embargo would assist the economy and people. It would boost Gazan economic growth, job creation, and access to basic products and services, improving living circumstances. It would also enable vital infrastructure development and greater movement and personal development. All sides must find a solution that satisfies security concerns and prioritizes Gazan rights and well-being.

Promoting Reconstruction and Development:

Gaza needs international funding to repair hospitals, schools, housing, and infrastructure. This would give immediate relief, jobs, and economic growth. Gaza must be rebuilt and developed to repair the damage inflicted by Israel's aggression and embargo. Thus, international aid should reconstruct and improve healthcare, education, and housing. This support would alleviate the affected populace, create jobs, and boost the economy. Building healthcare facilities could improve Gaza's health by boosting access to quality medical treatments. Rebuilding schools will ensure children have access to education, boosting their intellectual growth and possibilities. Building housing infrastructure would also help Gazans cope with the housing scarcity. International support for reconstruction and development can help Gazans achieve long-term stability, economic growth, and well-being. Access to healthcare in Gaza should be ensured. This involves simplifying medical supply and equipment imports, boosting healthcare professional training, and improving the healthcare system's emergency and public health response. The health of Gazans depends on uninterrupted healthcare availability. Healthcare access issues should be addressed. This includes importing and distributing medical supplies and equipment to Gazan hospitals quickly. Training and professional development for healthcare workers should also be supported to help them learn and sustain great care. Equally vital is improving the healthcare system's emergency and public health response. This requires infrastructural investment, healthcare management system improvements, and international health organization coordination. Secure access to healthcare and enhancing the healthcare system can improve Gaza's health and help its people live healthier lives.

Promoting Economic Opportunities:

To reduce poverty and unemployment, foster entrepreneurship, vocational training, and job development. Helping small firms, permitting microfinance, and investing in high-growth areas can boost economic growth and social possibilities. Join us in supporting these efforts and making positive change. Sustainable peace and Gazan living circumstances require a just and comprehensive Israeli-Palestinian agreement. We must address this conflict's causes to end it. We must prioritize a sovereign Palestinian state, recognize Palestinian rights and aspirations, and faithfully implement international accords. Only then can we hope for regional peace and stability. Israel's aggression has also affected Gaza's health, mortality, and economy. Stay informed by using credible sources and support policy ideas to reduce human suffering and find a just and sustainable solution to the conflict.

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